

MACHINING OF POLYETHYLENE-ALUMINUM COMPOSITE FROM USED BEVERAGE CARTON WASTE BY MILLING USING HIGH-SPEED CUTTING TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This research study the machining of Polyethylene-aluminum composite (PolyAl composite) by milling using high speed steel cutting tools. The composite plates from PolyAl were fabricated by two roll mill machine and compression machine. They are cut to size of 55 x 55 x 10 mm for machining testing by 3 axis CNC. In experiment, the factors of machining consist of feed rate, spindle speed and depth of cut. 2 types of cutting tool are studied with 2 flute high speed end mill and 4 flute high speed end mill. The experiments were designed by DOE of General full factorial. The surface roughness (R_a) was used to investigate for machining. The results, the machining by 2 flutes high speed end mill founded that R_a increase with an increase of feed rate, R_a decrease with an increase of spindle speed and R_a trends to decrease with an increase of depth of cut. The machining by 4 flutes high speed end mill founded that R_a increase with an increase of feed rate, R_a decrease with an increase of spindle speed and R_a trends to decrease with an increase of depth of cut. The optimal condition of 2 flutes high speed end mill was R_a of 1.914 μm by condition of feed rate 400 mm/min, spindle speed 1500 rpm and depth of cut 1 mm, and optimal condition of 4 flutes high speed end mill was R_a of 2.385 μm by condition of feed rate 1000 mm/min, spindle speed 1500 rpm and depth of cut 3 mm.

Methodology

PolyAl composite was fabricated by two roll mill and compression process. it was cut to size of 55*55 mm, then it was machined by 3 axis CNC milling. Different cutting conditions were studied as show in Table 1. The surface roughness was investigated in this work

Table 1. Cutting conditions

spindle speed (rpm)	500	1000	1500
Feed rate (mm/min)	400	1000	1600
depth of cut (mm)	1	3	6
cutting tools	high speed steel 2 flute, diameter of 6 mm		
spindle speed (rpm)	500	1000	1500
Feed rate (mm/min)	400	1000	1600
depth of cut (mm)	1	3	6
cutting tools	high speed steel 4 flute, diameter of 6 mm		

PolyAl

two roll mill

Hot compression

PolyAl composite

Machining position

Surface roughness tester

Results ; The machining by 2 flute high speed end mill

Table 2. Analysis of variance for R_a

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value
Feed rate (mm/min)	2	3.368	1.684	5.98	0.004
Spindle speed (rpm)	2	66.381	33.191	117.79	0.000
Depth of cut (mm)	2	15.371	7.686	27.27	0.000
Feed rate (mm/min)* Spindle speed (rpm)	4	4.832	1.208	4.29	0.003
Feed rate (mm/min)* Depth of cut (mm)	4	4.582	1.145	4.07	0.005
Spindle speed (rpm)* Depth of cut (mm)	4	4.619	1.154	4.10	0.004
Feed rate (mm/min)* Spindle speed (rpm)* Depth of cut (mm)	8	15.904	1.988	7.06	0.000
Error	81	22.824			
Total	107	137.88			

S = 0.530829 R-Sq = 83.45% R-Sq(adj) = 70.57%

The machining by 4 flute high speed end mill

Table 3. Analysis of variance for R_a

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value
Feed rate (mm/min)	2	1.723	0.861	1.29	0.282
Spindle speed (rpm)	2	35.126	17.563	26.24	0.000
Depth of cut (mm)	2	15.156	7.578	11.32	0.000
Feed rate (mm/min)* Spindle speed (rpm)	4	2.048	0.512	0.77	0.551
Feed rate (mm/min)* Depth of cut (mm)	4	1.619	0.404	0.60	0.660
Spindle speed (rpm)* Depth of cut (mm)	4	6.575	1.644	2.46	0.052
Feed rate (mm/min)* Spindle speed (rpm)* Depth of cut (mm)	8	11.436	1.430	2.14	0.041
Error	81	54.207	0.670		
Total	107	127.89			

S = 0.818 R-Sq = 57.61% R-Sq(adj) = 44.01%

Conclusion

The results, the optimal condition of using 2 flute high speed end mill was feed rate of 400 mm/min, spindle speed of 1500 rev/min and depth of cut 1 mm which R_a is 1.914. The optimal condition of using 4 flute high speed end mill was feed rate of 1000 mm/min, spindle speed of 1500 rev/min and depth of cut 3 mm which R_a is 2.385